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Career choice for nursing students in Kuwait

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ABSTRACT

Background: The process of entering nursing, as one of the pivotal healthcare discipline, certainly affects quality of care, and retention of nurses in the profession.

Aims: Exploring factors affecting the nursing students' decision to enter nursing and their attitude towards future career.

Subjects and methods: Ninety currently registered students in Nursing Institute, Kuwait participated in a cross-sectional study conducted in 2013. Self-administered questionnaire was used.

Results: Kuwaiti females outnumbered males, while the percentage of non-Kuwaiti males with undetermined nationality (bedoon) were higher than females. The majority of the students (88.9%) mentioned that they knew their future specialty after graduation. The first favorable specialties of the students were school health or primary health care followed by other specialties. Regarding the criteria for choosing nursing career, 48.9% reported like of work, 24.4% due to their scientific excellence, 23.3% due to work dedication, and 20.0% due to self-confidence, and 17.8% due to their committed practical work. The most important ambitions and priorities after graduation for the students were to get suitable work inside Kuwait, want work stability, and complete education.

Conclusions: Improving the complement of nurses, and changing the attitudes and perceptions towards them are crucial to recruit more students in nursing school.

Keywords: nursing students, career choice, attitude.

INTRODUCTION

The nurse is the single most important frontline health worker. Without nurses the clinics, community health centers and hospitals cannot function. (Ntshona, 2000) Many studies worldwide report that interest in nursing as a career is low. Only 5.2% of a sample of high school respondents in Saudi Arabia intended to pursue nursing after school. (Al-Omar, 2004) A study in Tanzania showed that, of all the medically related professions, nursing was the least popular with only 9% of students expressing an interest, (Kikwilu et al, 2000) whilst amongst Asian students in Australia less than 10% were interested in nursing as a profession. (Rossiter et al, 1998) In Kuwait, however, 19% of female high school students interviewed were considering nursing as a career (Al-Kandari et al, 2005) and in Hong Kong, this figure rose to 28%. (Law et al, 2003)

The reasons for the perceived lack of interest in nursing as a career are multi-factorial, and may differ from context to another. In South Africa, the low status of the profession, heavy workloads, and poor access to personal development programs have been proposed as some of the reasons learners are not attracted to nursing as a career. (Department of Health, 2006) Other negative perceptions about nursing are that the workload is physically demanding, and that the shortage of nurses increases the stress of the work. (Buerhaus et al, 2005) Of concern is that some of the perceptions about nursing do not reflect reality. These need to be corrected in order to attract more high school leavers to the profession. (Kohler et al, 1990) Positive perceptions include that nursing offers good job security, and that the shortage of nurses will lead to pay rises and wider choice of jobs. (Buerhaus et al, 2005) Many years ago nursing was seen to have numerous career advantages. These included a large demand for nurses nationwide, many job opportunities, various nursing career choices, good benefits, many choices both in terms of specialty areas and opportunities for advancement. (Prater et al, 2006)

Self-actualization is one of the most important reasons given for entering the nursing profession. Many students who choose nursing are motivated by a desire to help others, and have strong perceptions on how they will practice once qualified. (Zysberg et al, 2005 and Spouse, 2000) These perceptions are an important influence on whether or not nursing students complete their courses. However, not all students who choose nursing express a

calling or even a desire to do nursing as their first choice. In a Jordanian study, 69% of nursing students entered the profession because of family or economic pressures. (Jrasat, 2005) Similarly, in Turkey, many nurses entered the profession as a last resort, because they did not qualify for other university courses. (Baykal, 2005) Personality traits are considered crucial in the selection of a career in nursing, (Zak et al, 1979) with caring, compassion, (Prater et al, 2006) and resilience (McGee, 2006) considered some of the most important traits for nursing. One of the most important influences on students who take up a career in nursing is contact with a practicing nurse. Other important influences are friends, parents and other family members, the occupation of the mother, and experience of a hospital environment. (Law et al, 2003; Buerhaus et al, 2005)

Gender is a very powerful factor in the choice of nursing as a career. Women are more likely to consider nursing than men, (Kikwilu et al, 2000 and Law et al, 2003) and, for different reasons, women are more likely to cite self-actualization as their main motivation, whilst men are more likely to cite economic reasons. (Zysberg et al, 2005) Although numbers are increasing, men still comprise a minority in the nursing profession, and may be deterred from entering it by the perception that nursing is "women's work". (Romem et al, 2005)

The principal aim was to identify the nature of career choices available to learners in different nursing schools and to analyze the links between the careers chosen and the factors influencing those choices. The present study aims at exploring factors affecting the students' decision to enter nursing and their attitude towards their future career.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

This study is a cross-sectional survey that was conducted from October to December 2013 in the Nursing Institute, Kuwait. Ninety currently registered students were asked to participate in the study. Self-administered questionnaires were distributed to participants after obtaining their verbal consent to participate. In order to maintain confidentiality, questionnaires were made anonymous. The questionnaire was derived from other published studies dealing with the same topic as well as from our own experience.

The participants were interviewed for their personal characteristics, first favorable future nursing specialty after graduation, criteria for choosing nursing specialty, their attitude towards their future career, their beliefs about factors that may determine their future field of work and their ambitions and priorities after graduation.

Simple descriptive statistics were used (frequency with percentage distribution). The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS-17) was used for data processing.

RESULTS

Table 1 reveals that 50.0% of participant students were females, 25.6% were < 19 years, 35.6% aged 19-21 and 38.9% were ≥22 years old. Just less than half of participants (45.6%) were non-Kuwaiti whereas 32.2% were Kuwaiti and 22.2% were "Bedoon" (with undetermined nationality). More than half of participants completed the 10th level of education, whereas 17.8% completed the 11th level and 27.8% completed the 12th level or higher; and 52.2% had one or more relative working in the field of nursing.

Table 2 reveals the first favorable nursing specialty that students wish to work in after graduation. School health ranked first, where 22.2% of the student select it, primary health care (PHC) came second (15.6%), followed by surgery wards (11.1%), internal medicine or obstetrics & gynecology ward (8.9%). Other specialties came after. Intensive care unit came at the end of the list (2.2%). Male students selected PHC, surgery ward, and internal medicine in higher proportion than females, whereas higher proportions of female students selected school health and premature units than males.

Table 3 shows the criteria for choosing nursing specialty. About half of the students (48.9%) attributed their thoughts to their loving of this field of work, 23.3% due to work dedication, 24.4% due to their scientific excellence in the field, 20.0% due to self-confidence and fitting to their personality, 17.8% due to their commitment to practical work.

Table 4 shows nursing students' attitude towards their future career. The majority (88.9%) reported that they have knowledge about their future carrier, 73.3% believed that they will work in more than one specialty, 91.1% believed that they will work in their favorable specialty, and 71.1% thought that there are other factors beyond their control that will determine their field of work. When students were asked about these external factors outside the control of their will, table 5 showed that 80.0% mentioned the nationality, 27.8% mentioned the recommendation, 13.3% attributed this to laws and regulations, 12.2% reported customs and traditions, 8.9% residence, and 7.8% related this to the availability of employment opportunities.

Table 6 reveals the most important ambitions and priorities after graduation for the students. The ambitions and priorities of 38.9% of the students were to get suitable work inside Kuwait, 36.7% wanted work stability, 17.8% wanted to complete education, and only 3.3% wanted to work outside Kuwait.

Table 1: General characteristics of participating nursing students

Variable	No.	%
Gender		
Male	45	50.0
Female	45	50.0
Age		
<19	23	25.6
19-21	32	35.6
≥22	35	38.9
Nationality		
K	29	32.2
NK	41	45.6
Undetermined (Bedoon)	20	22.2
Qualification		
10th	49	54.4
11th	16	17.8
12th+	25	27.8
Relatives working in nursing		
N	43	47.8
Y	47	52.2
Total	90	100.0

Table 2: First favorable future nursing specialty of nursing students after graduation

Specialty	Male		Female		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
School health	9	20.0	11	24.4	20	22.2
Primary health care	11	24.4	3	6.7	14	15.6
Surgery ward	9	20.0	1	2.2	10	11.1
Internal medicine ward	5	11.1	3	6.7	8	8.9
Obstetrics and gynecology ward	4	8.9	4	8.9	8	8.9
Premature units	1	2.2	5	11.1	6	6.7
Delivery rooms	3	6.7	3	6.7	6	6.7
Operations theaters	2	4.4	4	8.9	6	6.7
Preventive care	3	6.7	2	4.4	5	5.6
Pediatric ward	3	6.7	2	4.4	5	5.6
Intensive care unit	2	4.4	0	0.0	2	2.2
Total	45	100.0	45	100.0	90	100.0

Table 3: Criteria for choosing nursing specialty

Criteria	Male (n=45)		Female (n=45)		Total (n=90)	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Like this specialty	23	51.1	21	46.7	44	48.9
Work dedication	10	22.2	11	24.4	21	23.3
Superior scientifically	12	26.7	10	22.2	22	24.4
Fit in personality and self-confident	8	17.8	10	22.2	18	20.0
Committed practical duties	11	24.4	5	11.1	16	17.8
Other reasons	3	6.7	3	6.7	6	6.7

Table 4: Nursing students' attitude towards their future career

Attitude	Male (n=45)		Female (n=45)		Total (n=90)	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Do you have knowledge of your future career						
No	3	6.7	7	15.6	10	11.1
Yes	42	93.3	38	84.4	80	88.9
Do you believe that you will work in more than one specialty						
No	12	26.7	12	26.7	24	26.7
Yes	33	73.3	33	73.3	66	73.3
Do you believe that you will work in your favorable specialty						
No	4	8.9	4	8.9	8	8.9
Yes	41	91.1	41	91.1	82	91.1
Do you think that there are other factors that will determine your field of nursing work.						
No	6	3.3	20	34.4	26	38.9
Yes	39	86.7	25	55.6	64	71.1

Table 5: Nursing student' beliefs about external factors that may determine their future field of nursing work

Factors	No	%
Recommendation	25	27.8
Nationality	72	80.0
Customs and traditions	11	12.2
Residence	8	8.9
Special circumstances	10	11.1
Laws and regulations	12	13.3
Availability of employment opportunities	7	7.8
Others	5	5.6

Table 6 : Nursing students' most important ambitions and priorities after graduation

Future ambition	No	%
Suitable work inside Kuwait	35	38.9
Work stability	33	36.7
Complete education	16	17.8
Work outside Kuwait	3	3.3
Other ambitions	3	3.3
Total	90	100.0

DISCUSSION

Nursing students come into nursing education with inherent lay beliefs of nursing that evolve over years of education, enabling them to be professionally socialized into the nursing career. A small number of research studies that addressed the impact of nursing students' perceptions of the public image of nursing were found. Although nursing students' perception of nursing and factors influencing it were well investigated in the West, this was less examined in the Arab Islamic region. Many of these studies suggest that factors such as latterly educational and career progression, socio-economic status, personal ability and parental encouragement are all influential in whether a person chooses nursing as a study choice. (Wallace, 2007; Kinzie et al, 2004)

Gender is a very powerful factor in the choice of nursing as a career. The sample of students in this study comprised 50.0% females and 50.0% males. Regarding nationality, Kuwaiti females outnumbered males, on the other hand, non-Kuwaiti male bedoon were higher than females. Women are more likely to consider nursing than

men, (Kikwilu et al, 2000 and Al-Kandari et al, 2005) and, for different reasons, women are more likely to cite self-actualization as their main motivation, whilst men are more likely to cite economic reasons. (Zysberg et al 2005) Although numbers are increasing, men still comprise a minority in the nursing profession, and may be deterred from entering it by the perception that nursing is “women’s work”. (Romem et al, 2005)

Parental influence plays a substantial part on students’ choice of nursing study. (Beggs et al, 2008) The current study reveals that more than a half of the students had relatives working in that career. These results were consistent with a recent study by Law and Arthurs that reported a 28% of sampled high school students were interested in studying nursing, and that their choice was significantly influenced by parental influence or demographic factors such as gender. (Law et al, 2003) A similar study by Harrigan et al identified parental pressure as the major factor in preventing the Native Hawaiian, Samoan and Filipino students from choosing nursing as their career. (Harrigan et al, 2003) According to a *Jordanian* study, the opinions of family members about nursing have influenced career decision making of their children, and so it is necessary to plan recruitment strategies that not alone attract nursing candidates, but also influence the perceptions of parents. (Al Jarrah, 2013) These results are supported by an earlier study on factors affecting students’ choice of nursing as a career in Egypt and Syria. The authors found that the family members had the significant impact on the choice of nursing as a career. (El-Sharkawy et al, 1995) An other study in Chicago reported that family members were the most encouraging forces to their entering nursing and was the main source of moral support during the years of schooling. (Kelly, 1996)

The results of current study reveals that the first favorable specialties of the students they wish to work in after graduation was school health and PHC, followed by surgery wards, internal medicine department, then Obstetrics & gynecology ward. Pediatric ward and ICU came as last choices. The majority of them believed that they will work in their favorable specialty. This could be attributed to the relatively low work load and absence (or lower rate) of night shifts in school health and PHC. There are various job opportunities for nurses in many different departments. Mostly nursing jobs can be obtained in hospitals, while clinics, home healthcare agencies, nursing homes, nursing schools, temporary help agencies, and government agencies provide various openings. (Sturo, 2007)

Regarding the reasons behind the students’ belief, in the present study, that they will work in the wanted specialty. About half of the students attributed their thoughts to their loving the work, 24.4% due to their scientific excellence, 23.3% due to work dedication, 20.0% due to self-confidence, 17.8% due to their committed practical work. This is supported by a similar study surveying 167 college entrants, which found that main factors influencing students’ college choice included intellectual and social emphases, practicality and advice of others. Nursing is frequently viewed as a vocation, even a “calling”. (Kinzie et al, 2006) Self-actualization is one of the most important reasons given for entering the nursing profession. Many students who choose nursing are motivated by a desire to help others, (Zysberg et al, 2005) and have strong perceptions on how they will practice once qualified. (Spouse, 2000) These perceptions are an important influence on whether or not nursing students complete their courses. However, not all students who choose nursing express a calling or even a desire to do nursing as their first choice. In a Jordanian study, 69% of nursing students entered the profession because of family or economic pressures. (Jrasat et al, 2005) Similarly in Turkey, many nurses entered the profession as a last resort, because they did not qualify for other university courses. (Bayka et al, 2005)

Finding of the present study is consistent with previous published research studies. (Abdel El-Halem et al, 2001; Eman et al, 2012; Patidar et al, 2012) In Jordan, little is known about Jordanian student nurses’ perception of nursing. (Safadi et al, 2011) Nursing students’ perceptions of nursing might have an impact on their self-concept, self-esteem, recruitment, retention, and performance. (Wallace, 2007) Extrinsic reasons as pay and conditions of work which were previously hardly mentioned at all, have increasing importance. A further new reason given for the choice of the career is the opportunity it offers for personal development. It is no longer enough to assume that for future students the motivation of wanting to be useful can be taken for granted, and that all that is necessary for maintaining it, are satisfactory working conditions. In order to ensure job satisfaction and to prevent frustration it will be essential to create conditions which ensure that the motivation to be useful remains intact but which also promote personal growth and development.

The shortage of nurses in Kuwait is attributed to low production of indigenous nurses, resignation and emigration of foreign nurses, and expansion of health care facilities. (Al-Kandari et al, 2005) There are many options available in nursing for those who want to pursue nursing as a profession. Nursing is a very diverse field and offers many different sectors to work in. (Sturo, 2007) Due to the low economic status in developing countries as Jordan, it is expected that more men will choose nursing as a career because nursing offers stable employment with high salaries. Nursing profession also drives students to work outside the country. In addition, it may be due to cultural values in Arab countries where males assume great responsibilities and it was expected to be the main reason for entering the nursing profession since the graduates are automatically hired and have the opportunities to work abroad whether in Arab or western countries. (Jrasat et al, 2005) However, this result is dissimilar to the results of a

study conducted in Egypt where availability of work and financial reward were the least mentioned reasons among her subjects, as the subjects of such study were female nursing students. (Gamel, 2006)

The current study revealed that the most important ambitions and priorities after graduation for the students were to get suitable work inside Kuwait, want work stability, want complete education, want work outside Kuwait and only 2.2% wanted other ambitions. In a previous study it was revealed that the highest percentage of study subjects joined the faculty of nursing because of financial reasons or availability of work. (Al Jarrah, 2013) Also, a study in Pennsylvania, revealed that nursing was attractive because of job opportunities, security and availability. (Streubert, 1994) This is also supported by an Egyptian study which found that around two-thirds of their subjects have chosen nursing as it represented a good opportunity for them to work. (Abdlkarim et al, 2004) Buerhaus et al., reported that slightly more than three quarters of the subjects joined nursing because of availability of work. (Buerhaus et al, 2005) Sand-Jecklin and Schaffer, added that students most frequently reported choosing nursing because of the availability of career opportunities, jobs security, salary, and interest in nursing. (Sand-Jecklin et al, 2006) Another study showed that students choose to study nursing because it offered work abroad and opportunities for further professional development. (Williams et al, 1997)

The perception that nursing is becoming less popular as a career choice amongst Kuwaiti school students required further investigation. Improving the complement of nurses in the country is crucial to improving quality of care. Only by investigating the multitude of factors that influence nursing school student in their career choices can attempts be made to attract more nurses into the profession. Some of these factors may be unique to the Kuwait context, while others may reflect wider international trends. However, once they are identified, targeted efforts can be made to change the attitudes and perceptions and so recruit more school leavers into the nursing profession.

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